

target CRM		Li	Co	Graphite	Ni	Al	Cu	P	Mn	
application/waste flow		cathode active material (CAM) in Li rechargeable batteries	cathode active material (CAM) in Li rechargeable batteries	anode active material (AAM) in Li rechargeable batteries	cathode active material (CAM) in Li rechargeable batteries	cathode current collector (CCC), casing, and partly cathode active material (CAM) in Li rechargeable batteries	anode current collector (ACC) and cables in Li rechargeable batteries	cathode active material (CAM) in Li rechargeable batteries	cathode active material (CAM) in Li rechargeable batteries	
EoL treatment scenario without CRM recovery		Pyrometallurgy: Recent pyrometallurgical processes, in which Li ends up in slag, do not recover Li from the slag Black mass export: A vast majority of batteries are mechanically pre-treated to obtain black mass, which is then exported (containing Li, Co, Mn, Ni, P, etc.).	Black mass export: A vast majority of batteries are mechanically pre-treated to obtain black mass, which is then exported (containing Li, Co, Mn, Ni, P, etc.).	All current EoL treatment scenarios are without graphite recovery	Black mass export: A vast majority of batteries are mechanically pre-treated to obtain black mass, which is then exported (containing Li, Co, Mn, Ni, P, etc.).	Pyrometallurgy: Recent pyrometallurgical processes, in which Al ends up in slag, do not recover Al from the slag. Al in cathode material not recovered at all.	unlikely scenario	All current EoL treatment scenarios are without P recovery	All current EoL treatment scenarios are without Mn recovery	
(Partially) existing or potential EoL treatment scenario with CRM recovery		Hydrometallurgy and pyrometallurgy (if lithium is recovered from slag)	Hydrometallurgy and pyrometallurgy	Theoretically possible, when undergoing hydrometallurgical process	Hydrometallurgy and pyrometallurgy	Al current collector foil separation during pre-treatment and subsequent remelting	Hydrometallurgy and pyrometallurgy	Theoretically possible, when undergoing hydrometallurgical process	Theoretically possible, when undergoing hydrometallurgical process	
Nb.	Criteria (affecting recoverability)	How to evaluate the criteria?								
design/input-specific criteria										
1.1	Dissipation and heterogeneity in product/waste flow (accumulation and mass fraction within a product/waste flow)	How dissipated is the CRM and/or the CRM containing application in the product? Is the CRM and/or CRM containing application accumulated in specific components? Is the CRM accumulated/enriched in parts of the waste flow or is it more widely distributed within the waste flow? How is the CRM mass fraction in relation to the ore grade (in the application/component/product/parts of the waste flow)?	# Li mainly incorporated in cathode active material (CAM) as metal oxides # Li also present in electrolyte, but only 1/10 of what is in CAM # Li content in batteries ~1-3 wt.% Li (in e-p CAM)	# Co only incorporated in cathode active material (CAM) as metal oxides # Co content in batteries 0 - 18 wt.%	# Graphite is always incorporated in the anode active material (AAM) and sometimes mixed with Silicon # Graphite content in batteries 15-28 wt.%	# Ni only incorporated in cathode active material (CAM) as metal oxides # Nickel content in batteries 0 - 22 wt.%	# In NCA batteries: Al incorporated in cathode active material (CAM) as Al oxide # In all chemistries: Al incorporated in cathode current collector (CCC), also used in battery cell and pack terminals, thermal conductors and battery cell casing # Al content in batteries 7 - 12 wt.%	# Cu is incorporated in anode current collector (ACC) foils, battery cell and pack terminals, and cables # Cu content in batteries 5-10 wt.%	# P is incorporated in cathode active material (CAM) as a metal phosphate (PO ₄ ³⁻) # P content in LFP and LFMP batteries (not including electrolyte salt) 0 - 7 wt.% respectively	# Mn is incorporated in cathode active material (CAM) as metal oxides (NMC, LMO, NCA and LFMP batteries) # Mn content in batteries 1 - 17 wt%, depending on the chemistry
1.2	Change in product design/input (changes in quantities, replacements, etc.)	What are the current developments regarding change in product design, especially change in CRM quantities and replacements? Are there expected input changes that will affect the waste flow?	# As Li is present in all LIB cathode chemistries, it cannot be replaced # Sodium-ion-batteries (SIBs) have been introduced for EVs not containing Li, but market shares are still close to 0 in EU	# Current trend is moving to less Co and more Ni containing products # Current trend is also moving towards no Co containing products (e.g. LFP, LFMP)	# Graphite is contained in all LIB and SIB battery products # Trend is going towards synthetic graphite	# Current trend is moving to less Co and more Ni containing products	# Current trend is moving towards products with CAM without Al (EVs) # Current trend in CCC is moving towards high purity alumina (HPA) and pure Al sulphate, as well as usage of "mixed materials" in (EV) battery casing # On the other hand, completely new product: Al-ion batteries (AIB)	# Development of ultralight and ultrathin Cu current collectors; reduction of weight, improvement of energy density	# Current trend is moving towards products with higher energy density and lower P content (LFMP)	# Current trend in NMC chemistry is moving towards very low concentrations of Mn # On the other hand, current trend is moving away from LFP (without Mn) towards LFMP, where Mn is included
1.3	Product information and labelling (identifiability of CRM containing applications and components)	Does the product labelling provide sufficient information about the mass fraction and location of CRM in the product? Is there a required or voluntary labelling?	# Currently very limited information, only battery type (e.g. NiMH, NiCd, LIB, etc.) is indicated on battery cells # Battery Passport (DPP) introduced in 2027. Still unclear if exact amount of CRMs will be labelled. DPP only for EVs, LMTs and industrial batteries (<2kWh).	# Currently very limited information, only battery type (e.g. NiMH, NiCd, LIB, etc.) is indicated on battery cells # Battery Passport (DPP) introduced in 2027. Still unclear if exact amount of CRMs will be labelled. DPP only for EVs, LMTs and industrial batteries (<2kWh).	# Currently very limited information, only battery type (e.g. NiMH, NiCd, LIB, etc.) is indicated on battery cells # Battery Passport (DPP) introduced in 2027. Still unclear if exact amount of CRMs will be labelled. DPP only for EVs, LMTs and industrial batteries (<2kWh).	# Currently very limited information, only battery type (e.g. NiMH, NiCd, LIB, etc.) is indicated on battery cells # Battery Passport (DPP) introduced in 2027. Still unclear if exact amount of CRMs will be labelled. DPP only for EVs, LMTs and industrial batteries (<2kWh).	# Currently very limited information, only battery type (e.g. NiMH, NiCd, LIB, etc.) is indicated on battery cells # Battery Passport (DPP) introduced in 2027. Still unclear if exact amount of CRMs will be labelled. DPP only for EVs, LMTs and industrial batteries (<2kWh).	# Currently very limited information, only battery type (e.g. NiMH, NiCd, LIB, etc.) is indicated on battery cells # Battery Passport (DPP) introduced in 2027. Still unclear if exact amount of CRMs will be labelled. DPP only for EVs, LMTs and industrial batteries (<2kWh).	# Currently very limited information, only battery type (e.g. NiMH, NiCd, LIB, etc.) is indicated on battery cells # Battery Passport (DPP) introduced in 2027. Still unclear if exact amount of CRMs will be labelled. DPP only for EVs, LMTs and industrial batteries (<2kWh).	# Currently very limited information, only battery type (e.g. NiMH, NiCd, LIB, etc.) is indicated on battery cells # Battery Passport (DPP) introduced in 2027. Still unclear if exact amount of CRMs will be labelled. DPP only for EVs, LMTs and industrial batteries (<2kWh).
waste flow-specific criteria										
2.1	Dissipation in waste flow	How high is the mass fraction of the CRM in the (collected) waste flow (in relation to the ore grade)? How is the CRM containing application collected (e.g. application-, component-, product-level, mixed with other products)? Is there a pre-sorting of components or products? Is there a pre-sorting regarding input material/parts of the waste flow?	# As Lithium is contained in all LIBs, the dissipation in the overall waste LIB stream is smaller than for other constituents # Portable batteries are collected by official collection schemes; battery types are collected mixed (with other types) and pre-sorted before recycling processes # For portable and LMT batteries, collection rates set in Battery Regulation to boost the collection (mixed chemistries + pre-sorting) # No set collection rates or official collection schemes for EV and industrial batteries, but manufacturers and dealers obligatory to take them back. Also unofficial collection schemes available (mixed chemistries + pre-sorting).	# Portable batteries are collected by official collection schemes; battery types are collected mixed (with other types) and pre-sorted before recycling processes # For portable and LMT batteries, collection rates set in Battery Regulation to boost the collection (mixed chemistries + pre-sorting) # No set collection rates or official collection schemes for EV and industrial batteries, but manufacturers and dealers obligatory to take them back. Also unofficial collection schemes available (mixed chemistries + pre-sorting).	# As Graphite is contained in all LIBs, the dissipation in the overall waste LIB stream is smaller than for other constituents # Portable batteries are collected by official collection schemes; battery types are collected mixed (with other types) and pre-sorted before recycling processes # For portable and LMT batteries, collection rates set in Battery Regulation to boost the collection (mixed chemistries + pre-sorting) # No set collection rates or official collection schemes for EV and industrial batteries, but manufacturers and dealers obligatory to take them back. Also unofficial collection schemes available (mixed chemistries + pre-sorting).	# Portable batteries are collected by official collection schemes; battery types are collected mixed (with other types) and pre-sorted before recycling processes # For portable and LMT batteries, collection rates set in Battery Regulation to boost the collection (mixed chemistries + pre-sorting) # No set collection rates or official collection schemes for EV and industrial batteries, but manufacturers and dealers obligatory to take them back. Also unofficial collection schemes available (mixed chemistries + pre-sorting).	# Portable batteries are collected by official collection schemes; battery types are collected mixed (with other types) and pre-sorted before recycling processes # For portable and LMT batteries, collection rates set in Battery Regulation to boost the collection (mixed chemistries + pre-sorting) # No set collection rates or official collection schemes for EV and industrial batteries, but manufacturers and dealers obligatory to take them back. Also unofficial collection schemes available (mixed chemistries + pre-sorting).	# Portable batteries are collected by official collection schemes; battery types are collected mixed (with other types) and pre-sorted before recycling processes # For portable and LMT batteries, collection rates set in Battery Regulation to boost the collection (mixed chemistries + pre-sorting) # No set collection rates or official collection schemes for EV and industrial batteries, but manufacturers and dealers obligatory to take them back. Also unofficial collection schemes available (mixed chemistries + pre-sorting).	# Portable batteries are collected by official collection schemes; battery types are collected mixed (with other types) and pre-sorted before recycling processes # For portable and LMT batteries, collection rates set in Battery Regulation to boost the collection (mixed chemistries + pre-sorting) # No set collection rates or official collection schemes for EV and industrial batteries, but manufacturers and dealers obligatory to take them back. Also unofficial collection schemes available (mixed chemistries + pre-sorting).	# Portable batteries are collected by official collection schemes; battery types are collected mixed (with other types) and pre-sorted before recycling processes # For portable and LMT batteries, collection rates set in Battery Regulation to boost the collection (mixed chemistries + pre-sorting) # No set collection rates or official collection schemes for EV and industrial batteries, but manufacturers and dealers obligatory to take them back. Also unofficial collection schemes available (mixed chemistries + pre-sorting).
2.2	Mineralogical state	In which mineralogical state is the CRM in the application or waste flow (e.g. metal, oxide, etc.)?	# Metal Oxide in CAM # Dissolved in organic solvent as ions	# Metal Oxide in CAM	# Graphite is a crystalline allotrope (form) of the element carbon	# Metal Oxide in CAM	# Metal Oxide in CAM # Metallic Al in CCC	# Metallic Cu in ACC	# Metal phosphate in CAM	# Metal oxide in CAM

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2.3	Product and/or component collection (collection and return rates)	How high are the collection and return rates? Why are they high/low?	# Highly depends on the product they are incorporated in # Collection schemes, for portable batteries	# Highly depends on the product they are incorporated in # Collection schemes, for portable batteries	# Highly depends on the product they are incorporated in # Collection schemes, for portable batteries	# Highly depends on the product they are incorporated in # Collection schemes, for portable batteries	# Highly depends on the product they are incorporated in # Collection schemes, for portable batteries	# Highly depends on the product they are incorporated in # In EU still very low; EU's concentration on NMC chemistries and LFMP just emerging	# Highly depends on the product they are incorporated in
2.4	Current waste generated	Which waste quantities are currently generated? 2025	4720 t	13503 t	38542 t	12718 t	18720 t	17477 t	1358 t
2.5	Future waste generated	Which waste quantities are expected to be generated in the future? 2030 2035 2040	6830 t 11027 t 18492 t Strong increase	18114 t 22745 t 27739 t Strong increase	59233 t 98665 t 164942 t Very strong increase	19384 t 34653 t 61398 t Very strong increase	# Includes materials in battery packs (e.g. thermal conductors) 27002 t 48488 t 94089 t Very strong increase	# Includes materials in battery packs (e.g. cables) 26893 t 47672 t 89365 t Very strong increase	3575 t 9398 t 23302 t Very strong increase
technical criteria									
3.1	Availability of identification technology for CRM containing application/material/component/product	Is there a technology to identify the CRM containing application/component/product to enable its recovery?	# Battery type can be identified through label on the product (e.g. NiMH, alkaline, LIB, etc.) or based on the product they are incorporated in # Cathode chemistry is only sometimes known, e.g. in case of batteries from EVs # Generally, user electronics have high Ni and Co content	# Battery type can be identified through label on the product (e.g. NiMH, alkaline, LIB, etc.) or based on the product they are incorporated in # Cathode chemistry is only sometimes known, e.g. in case of batteries from EVs # Generally, user electronics have high Ni and Co content	# Battery type can be identified through label on the product (e.g. NiMH, alkaline, LIB, etc.) or based on the product they are incorporated in # Generally, user electronics have high Ni and Co content	# Battery type can be identified through label on the product (e.g. NiMH, alkaline, LIB, etc.) or based on the product they are incorporated in # Cathode chemistry is only sometimes known, e.g. in case of batteries from EVs # Generally, user electronics have high Ni and Co content	# Battery type can be identified through label on the product (e.g. NiMH, alkaline, LIB, etc.) or based on the product they are incorporated in # Cathode chemistry is only sometimes known, e.g. in case of batteries from EVs # Generally, user electronics have high Ni and Co content # In battery packs, disassembly separation of non-ferrous metals from housing	# Battery type can be identified through label on the product (e.g. NiMH, alkaline, LIB, etc.) or based on the product they are incorporated in # Generally, user electronics have high Ni and Co content # In battery packs, disassembly separation of non-ferrous metals from housing	# Battery type can be identified through label on the product (e.g. NiMH, alkaline, LIB, etc.) or based on the product they are incorporated in # Cathode chemistry is only sometimes known, e.g. in case of batteries from EVs # Generally, user electronics have high Ni and Co content
3.2	Manual removability of CRM containing application/material/component (selective)	Is it possible to manually remove the CRM containing application or material from the product/waste flow (Is it screwed, glued, welded)?	# No, not possible	# No, not possible	# No, not possible	# No, not possible	# Yes, partly (housing of battery packs)	# Yes, partly (housing of battery packs)	# No, not possible
3.3	Automated removability of CRM containing application/material/components (selective removal)	Are processes available to remove the CRM containing application/component by automation? What is its TRL level?	# A new technology called "Direct Recycling" is able to separate different components (e.g. CAM, AAM, casing, etc.). However, this until now is only being applied to LFP batteries with a very specific format and in small numbers.	# A new technology called "Direct Recycling" is able to separate different components (e.g. CAM, AAM, casing, etc.). However, this until now is only being applied to LFP batteries with a very specific format and in small numbers.	# A new technology called "Direct Recycling" is able to separate different components (e.g. CAM, AAM, casing, etc.). However, this until now is only being applied to LFP batteries with a very specific format and in small numbers.	# A new technology called "Direct Recycling" is able to separate different components (e.g. CAM, AAM, casing, etc.). However, this until now is only being applied to LFP batteries with a very specific format and in small numbers.	# Unknown	# Unknown	# A new technology called "Direct Recycling" is able to separate different components (e.g. CAM, AAM, casing, etc.). However, this until now is only being applied to LFP batteries with a very specific format and in small numbers.
3.4	Identifiability and separability of CRM containing material after liberation	Is it possible to identify and sort the CRM containing materials after liberation (e.g. shredding)? This can be without preceding removal/sorting or after preceding removal.	# Yes, as black mass	# Yes, as black mass	# Yes, as black mass	# Yes, as black mass	# Al from CCCs can be separated in mechanical separation # Non-ferrous metals can be separated from a waste flow by eddy current separation # The non-ferrous metal fraction can be further separated by density separation or XRT sensor-based sorting into a Cu and Al fraction # Al scrap can be sorted according to alloy type or series with LIBS or other sensor-based sorting technologies. Sensor-based sorting technologies are limited to Al scrap with high mass fraction of alloying elements and low variability within the fractions that should be separated # Separation of Al in CAM not possible	# Cu from ACC can be separated in mechanical separation # Non-ferrous metals can be separated from a waste flow by eddy current separation # The non-ferrous metal fraction can be further separated by density separation or XRT sensor-based sorting into a Cu and Al fraction	# Yes, as black mass

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Nb.	Criteria (affecting recoverability)	How to evaluate the criteria?								
3.5	Ability to concentrate CRM containing material / mechanically remove impurities	Is it possible to concentrate or to mechanically remove impurities from the CRM containing material flow?	# Black mass undergoes various sorting and separation steps to achieve the lowest possible impurity level (e.g. Al, Cu, plastic)	# Black mass undergoes various sorting and separation steps to achieve the lowest possible impurity level (e.g. Al, Cu, plastic)	# Black mass undergoes various sorting and separation steps to achieve the lowest possible impurity level (e.g. Al, Cu, plastic)	# Black mass undergoes various sorting and separation steps to achieve the lowest possible impurity level (e.g. Al, Cu, plastic)	# Al CCC can have impurities from CAM and cathode polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) binder, that are difficult to remove	# Cu ACC can have impurities from graphite (AAM) and cathode polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) binder, that are difficult to remove	# Black mass undergoes various sorting and separation steps to achieve the lowest possible impurity level (e.g. Al, Cu, plastic)	# Black mass undergoes various sorting and separation steps to achieve the lowest possible impurity level (e.g. Al, Cu, plastic)
3.6	Ability to thermally and/or chemically separate and refine CRMs from concentrates	Is there a thermal and/or chemical recovery technology for the CRM? What is its TRL level?	# Hydrometallurgy can produce target element carbonates (e.g. LiCO ₃)	# Pyrometallurgy produces a Cobalt-Nickel-Copper-Iron Alloy, separating those metals from more oxidative Al, Li, Mn, etc. # Hydrometallurgy can produce target element sulphates (e.g. CoSO ₄)	# Flotation of black mass to separate graphite # Further graphite can be chemically refined or calcinated (thermal treatment), but not done in EU # One company already recycles Graphite in Sweden (Vianode) - TRL9	# Pyrometallurgy produces a Cobalt-Nickel-Copper-Iron Alloy, separating those metals from more oxidative Al, Li, Mn, etc. # Hydrometallurgy can produce target element sulphates (e.g. NiSO ₄)	# Al separated via mechanical separation can be reintroduced into the Al cycle # For functional recycling, purity requirements of the input material for remelting are high as the refining possibilities are limited # Pyrometallurgy produces a Cobalt-Nickel-Copper-Iron Alloy, separating those metals from more oxidative Al, Li, Mn, etc. # Al treated as impurity, ends up in slag or residuals	# Cu separated via mechanical separation can be reintroduced into the Cu cycle # Pyrometallurgy produces a Cobalt-Nickel-Copper-Iron Alloy, separating those metals from more oxidative Al, Li, Mn, etc.	# In pyrometallurgy, P treated as impurity, ends up in slag # Hydrometallurgy can produce target element solutions (e.g. HPO ₄ ²⁻ /H ₂ PO ₄), but not done in EU	# In pyrometallurgy, Mn treated as impurity, ends up in slag # Hydrometallurgy can produce target element sulphates (MnSO ₄), but not done in EU
economic criteria										
4.1	Market and quality of 2CRM	Is there a market for the 2CRM? What is the quality of the 2CRM compared to the primary one? How volatile is the market?	# Currently low demand for recyclates, as there is close to no cell or CAM production in EU # Demand increases prospectively # Possible impurities lower the quality # Battery Regulation requires recycled content for EV, LMT, SLI and industrial batteries (<2kWh): 6% Li (2031, except LMT), 12% Li (2036)	# Currently close to no demand for recyclates, as there is close to no cell or CAM production in EU # Demand increases prospectively # Possible impurities lower the quality # Battery Regulation requires recycled content for EV, LMT, SLI and industrial batteries (<2kWh): 16% Co (2031, except LMT), 26% Co (2036)	# Currently low demand, as there is close to no cell or CAM production in EU # Demand increases prospectively # Possible impurities lower the quality	# Currently low demand for recyclates, as there is close to no cell or CAM production in EU # Demand increases prospectively # Possible impurities lower the quality # Battery Regulation requires recycled content for EV, LMT, SLI and industrial batteries (<2kWh): 6% Ni (2031, except LMT), 15% Ni (2036)	# There is an Al scrap market # Oftentimes, Al scrap is not sorted according to alloy type or series and can only be downcycled to cast Al or ends up as scrap surplus # Non-ferrous metal scrap which is a mix of Al, Cu and other alloys is traded and can be e.g. used as input material for an integrated Cu smelter where Al ends up in the slag # Quality in battery grade requires complex and costly refining process	# There is a Cu scrap market # Quality in battery grade requires complex and costly refining process	# Currently no demand for recyclates, as there is close to no cell or CAM production in Europe # Demand increases prospectively # No LFP production in Europe	# Currently no demand for recyclates, as there is close to no cell or CAM production in Europe # Demand increases prospectively
4.2	Price competition of 2CRM with primary	Would it be cheaper to use the waste flow instead of an ore to recover the CRM?	# In general, secondary CRMs are much more expensive than from primary production (expert opinion) # Strong competition from Asian recycling markets # Potential profitability highly dependent on recycling technology (pyro- or hydrometallurgy) # Hydrometallurgy less susceptible to price fluctuations or target materials and to input feed (battery chemistry) # Hydrometallurgy expected to be more profitable particularly when scaled up # Rising prices in CO ₂ certificates make it more challenging for pyrometallurgy to work financially viable (Woeste et al., 2024)	# Secondary CRMs can be price-competitive with primary production (expert opinion) # Strong competition from Asian recycling markets # Potential profitability highly dependent on recycling technology (pyro- or hydrometallurgy) # Hydrometallurgy less susceptible to price fluctuations or target materials and to input feed (battery chemistry) # Hydrometallurgy expected to be more profitable particularly when scaled up # Rising prices in CO ₂ certificates make it more challenging for pyrometallurgy to work financially viable (Woeste et al., 2024)	# In general, secondary CRMs are much more expensive than from primary production (expert opinion) # Strong competition from Asian recycling markets # Potential profitability highly dependent on recycling technology (pyro- or hydrometallurgy) # Hydrometallurgy less susceptible to price fluctuations or target materials and to input feed (battery chemistry) # Hydrometallurgy expected to be more profitable particularly when scaled up # Rising prices in CO ₂ certificates make it more challenging for pyrometallurgy to work financially viable (Woeste et al., 2024)	# Secondary CRMs can be price-competitive with primary production (expert opinion) # Strong competition from Asian recycling markets # Potential profitability highly dependent on recycling technology (pyro- or hydrometallurgy) # Hydrometallurgy less susceptible to price fluctuations or target materials and to input feed (battery chemistry) # Hydrometallurgy expected to be more profitable particularly when scaled up # Rising prices in CO ₂ certificates make it more challenging for pyrometallurgy to work financially viable (Woeste et al., 2024)	# The price for Al scrap depends on its quality and the demand for that quality on the market # There is no direct price competition between primary and secondary Al # Not every quality can be achieved with secondary Al	# There is no price different between primary and secondary Cu	# In general, secondary CRMs are much more expensive than from primary production (expert opinion) # Strong competition from Asian recycling markets # Potential profitability highly dependent on recycling technology (pyro- or hydrometallurgy) # Hydrometallurgy less susceptible to price fluctuations or target materials and to input feed (battery chemistry) # Hydrometallurgy expected to be more profitable particularly when scaled up # Rising prices in CO ₂ certificates make it more challenging for pyrometallurgy to work financially viable (Woeste et al., 2024)	# In general, secondary CRMs are much more expensive than from primary production (expert opinion) # Strong competition from Asian recycling markets # Potential profitability highly dependent on recycling technology (pyro- or hydrometallurgy) # Hydrometallurgy less susceptible to price fluctuations or target materials and to input feed (battery chemistry) # Hydrometallurgy expected to be more profitable particularly when scaled up # Rising prices in CO ₂ certificates make it more challenging for pyrometallurgy to work financially viable (Woeste et al., 2024)

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application/waste flow		cathode active material (CAM) in Li rechargeable batteries	cathode active material (CAM) in Li rechargeable batteries	anode active material (AAM) in Li rechargeable batteries	cathode active material (CAM) in Li rechargeable batteries	cathode current collector (CCC), casing, and partly cathode active material (CAM) in Li rechargeable batteries	anode current collector (ACC) and cables in Li rechargeable batteries	cathode active material (CAM) in Li rechargeable batteries	cathode active material (CAM) in Li rechargeable batteries	
EoL treatment scenario without CRM recovery		Pyrometallurgy: Recent pyrometallurgical processes, in which Li ends up in slag, do not recover Li from the slag Black mass export: A vast majority of batteries are mechanically pre-treated to obtain black mass, which is then exported (containing Li, Co, Mn, Ni, P, etc.).	Black mass export: A vast majority of batteries are mechanically pre-treated to obtain black mass, which is then exported (containing Li, Co, Mn, Ni, P, etc.).	All current EoL treatment scenarios are without graphite recovery	Black mass export: A vast majority of batteries are mechanically pre-treated to obtain black mass, which is then exported (containing Li, Co, Mn, Ni, P, etc.).	Pyrometallurgy: Recent pyrometallurgical processes, in which Al ends up in slag, do not recover Al from the slag. Al in cathode material not recovered at all.	unlikely scenario	All current EoL treatment scenarios are without P recovery	All current EoL treatment scenarios are without Mn recovery	
(Partially) existing or potential EoL treatment scenario with CRM recovery		Hydrometallurgy and pyrometallurgy (if lithium is recovered from slag)	Hydrometallurgy and pyrometallurgy	Theoretically possible, when undergoing hydrometallurgical process	Hydrometallurgy and pyrometallurgy	Al current collector foil separation during pre-treatment and subsequent remelting	Hydrometallurgy and pyrometallurgy	Theoretically possible, when undergoing hydrometallurgical process	Theoretically possible, when undergoing hydrometallurgical process	
Nb.	Criteria (affecting recoverability)	How to evaluate the criteria?								
4.3	Economic incentives	Do specific economic incentives exist (tax related, fees, etc.) to recover the CRM? Are there other materials or elements driving the recovery?	# Not specific for CRMs # Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) obligates manufactures to take back and recycle batteries --> better recyclability or higher use of recycled content leads to lower fees --> cost savings in designing for recycling	# Not specific for CRMs # Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) obligates manufactures to take back and recycle batteries --> better recyclability or higher use of recycled content leads to lower fees --> cost savings in designing for recycling	# Not specific for CRMs # Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) obligates manufactures to take back and recycle batteries --> better recyclability or higher use of recycled content leads to lower fees --> cost savings in designing for recycling	# Not specific for CRMs # Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) obligates manufactures to take back and recycle batteries --> better recyclability or higher use of recycled content leads to lower fees --> cost savings in designing for recycling	# Not specific for CRMs # Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) obligates manufactures to take back and recycle batteries --> better recyclability or higher use of recycled content leads to lower fees --> cost savings in designing for recycling	# Not specific for CRMs # Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) obligates manufactures to take back and recycle batteries --> better recyclability or higher use of recycled content leads to lower fees --> cost savings in designing for recycling	# Not specific for CRMs # Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) obligates manufactures to take back and recycle batteries --> better recyclability or higher use of recycled content leads to lower fees --> cost savings in designing for recycling	# Not specific for CRMs # Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) obligates manufactures to take back and recycle batteries --> better recyclability or higher use of recycled content leads to lower fees --> cost savings in designing for recycling
4.4	Economically viable case studies	Are there (potentially) economically viable case studies for the recovery of the CRM? Does the value or the quantity of the CRM play a decisive role?	No	No	Unknown	No	Yes	Yes	No	No
4.5	Recycling conflicts with other materials or elements (especially more valuable ones)	Is there a recycling conflict with other materials or elements, especially with more valuable ones in the product/waste flow?	Ni and Co	No	Ni, Co, Li and Cu are more valuable	Co is more valuable	Ni, Co, Li and Cu are more valuable	Ni, Co and Li more valuable	Li is more valuable	Ni, Co, Li and Cu are more valuable
environmental criteria										
5.1	Logistics and infrastructure	How are the logistic and infrastructure requirements for the recovery process (process steps, distances, etc.)? Can existing infrastructure be used?	# Take back / collection schemes for batteries exist # Generally speaking, there are recycling plants, but not recovering CRMs to the full extend (often only mechanical recycling with black mass exports)	# Take back / collection schemes for batteries exist # Generally speaking, there are recycling plants, but not recovering CRMs to the full extend (often only mechanical recycling with black mass exports)	# Take back / collection schemes for batteries exist # Generally speaking, there are recycling plants, but not recovering CRMs to the full extend (often only mechanical recycling with black mass exports)	# Take back / collection schemes for batteries exist # Generally speaking, there are recycling plants, but not recovering CRMs to the full extend (often only mechanical recycling with black mass exports)	# Take back / collection schemes for batteries exist # There is an established infrastructure for Al recycling (sorting and remelting) # LIBS is an emerging technology enabling higher quality recycling separating 5000 and 6000 series Al # To establish the necessary logistics, a minimum volume of Al scrap is needed	# Take back / collection schemes for batteries exist # There is an established infrastructure for Cu recycling, both direct remelting or integrated smelters for more complex waste flows	# Take back / collection schemes for batteries exist # Generally speaking, there are recycling plants, but not recovering CRMs to the full extend (often only mechanical recycling with black mass exports)	# Take back / collection schemes for batteries exist # Generally speaking, there are recycling plants, but not recovering CRMs to the full extend (often only mechanical recycling with black mass exports)
5.2	Energy and chemical requirements for separation and sorting	What are the energy and chemical requirements for mechanical separation and sorting?	# Separation and sorting: 0.4-0.58 kWh/kg depending on cell type (pouch, cylinder, prismatic) # Depends on product and technology used, as well as the location of the facility (Romero Guillen et al., 2024)	# Separation and sorting: 0.4-0.58 kWh/kg depending on cell type (pouch, cylinder, prismatic) # Depends on product and technology used, as well as the location of the facility (Romero Guillen et al., 2024)	# Separation and sorting: 0.4-0.58 kWh/kg depending on cell type (pouch, cylinder, prismatic) # Depends on product and technology used, as well as the location of the facility (Romero Guillen et al., 2024)	# Separation and sorting: 0.4-0.58 kWh/kg depending on cell type (pouch, cylinder, prismatic) # Depends on product and technology used, as well as the location of the facility (Romero Guillen et al., 2024)	# Separation and sorting: 0.4-0.58 kWh/kg depending on cell type (pouch, cylinder, prismatic) # Depends on product and technology used, as well as the location of the facility (Romero Guillen et al., 2024)	# Separation and sorting: 0.4-0.58 kWh/kg depending on cell type (pouch, cylinder, prismatic) # Depends on product and technology used, as well as the location of the facility (Romero Guillen et al., 2024)	# Separation and sorting: 0.4-0.58 kWh/kg depending on cell type (pouch, cylinder, prismatic) # Depends on product and technology used, as well as the location of the facility (Romero Guillen et al., 2024)	# Separation and sorting: 0.4-0.58 kWh/kg depending on cell type (pouch, cylinder, prismatic) # Depends on product and technology used, as well as the location of the facility (Romero Guillen et al., 2024)
5.3	Energy and chemical requirements for thermal and/or chemical recovery	What are the energy and chemical requirements for thermal and/or (bio)chemical recovery in comparison with primary production?	# Energy: Depends on (and varies among) the product, battery chemistry, and the used recycling technology, as well as the location of the facility # Pyrometallurgy requires the most energy (smelting: 1389 kWh/t spent LIBs), followed by hydrometallurgy and direct recycling # Common chemicals in hydrometallurgy: H ₂ SO ₄ and H ₂ O ₂ (leaching); NH ₃ , Na ₂ CO ₃ (precipitation/recovery) (Rinne et al., 2021) (Wagner-Renz et al., 2023)	# Energy: Depends on (and varies among) the product, battery chemistry, and the used recycling technology, as well as the location of the facility # Pyrometallurgy requires the most energy (smelting: 1389 kWh/t spent LIBs), followed by hydrometallurgy and direct recycling # Common chemicals in hydrometallurgy: H ₂ SO ₄ and H ₂ O ₂ (leaching); NH ₃ , Na ₂ CO ₃ (precipitation/recovery) (Rinne et al., 2021) (Wagner-Renz et al., 2023)	# Energy: Depends on (and varies among) the product, battery chemistry, and the used recycling technology, as well as the location of the facility # Pyrometallurgy requires the most energy (smelting: 1389 kWh/t spent LIBs), followed by hydrometallurgy and direct recycling # Common chemicals in hydrometallurgy: H ₂ SO ₄ and H ₂ O ₂ (leaching); NH ₃ , Na ₂ CO ₃ (precipitation/recovery) (Rinne et al., 2021) (Wagner-Renz et al., 2023)	# Energy: Depends on (and varies among) the product, battery chemistry, and the used recycling technology, as well as the location of the facility # Pyrometallurgy requires the most energy (smelting: 1389 kWh/t spent LIBs), followed by hydrometallurgy and direct recycling # Common chemicals in hydrometallurgy: H ₂ SO ₄ and H ₂ O ₂ (leaching); NH ₃ , Na ₂ CO ₃ (precipitation/recovery) (Rinne et al., 2021) (Wagner-Renz et al., 2023)	# Metallic Al can be separated and reintroduced in Al-smelter	# Cu can be separated and reintroduced in Cu-smelter	# Energy: Depends on (and varies among) the product, battery chemistry, and the used recycling technology, as well as the location of the facility # Pyrometallurgy requires the most energy (smelting: 1389 kWh/t spent LIBs), followed by hydrometallurgy and direct recycling # Common chemicals in hydrometallurgy: H ₂ SO ₄ and H ₂ O ₂ (leaching); NH ₃ , Na ₂ CO ₃ (precipitation/recovery) (Rinne et al., 2021) (Wagner-Renz et al., 2023)	# Energy: Depends on (and varies among) the product, battery chemistry, and the used recycling technology, as well as the location of the facility # Pyrometallurgy requires the most energy (smelting: 1389 kWh/t spent LIBs), followed by hydrometallurgy and direct recycling # Common chemicals in hydrometallurgy: H ₂ SO ₄ and H ₂ O ₂ (leaching); NH ₃ , Na ₂ CO ₃ (precipitation/recovery) (Rinne et al., 2021) (Wagner-Renz et al., 2023)

target CRM		Li	Co	Graphite	Ni	Al	Cu	P	Mn
application/waste flow		cathode active material (CAM) in Li rechargeable batteries	cathode active material (CAM) in Li rechargeable batteries	anode active material (AAM) in Li rechargeable batteries	cathode active material (CAM) in Li rechargeable batteries	cathode current collector (CCC), casing, and partly cathode active material (CAM) in Li rechargeable batteries	anode current collector (ACC) and cables in Li rechargeable batteries	cathode active material (CAM) in Li rechargeable batteries	cathode active material (CAM) in Li rechargeable batteries
EoL treatment scenario without CRM recovery		Pyrometallurgy: Recent pyrometallurgical processes, in which Li ends up in slag, do not recover Li from the slag Black mass export: A vast majority of batteries are mechanically pre-treated to obtain black mass, which is then exported (containing Li, Co, Mn, Ni, P, etc.).	Black mass export: A vast majority of batteries are mechanically pre-treated to obtain black mass, which is then exported (containing Li, Co, Mn, Ni, P, etc.).	All current EoL treatment scenarios are without graphite recovery	Black mass export: A vast majority of batteries are mechanically pre-treated to obtain black mass, which is then exported (containing Li, Co, Mn, Ni, P, etc.).	Pyrometallurgy: Recent pyrometallurgical processes, in which Al ends up in slag, do not recover Al from the slag. Al in cathode material not recovered at all.	unlikely scenario	All current EoL treatment scenarios are without P recovery	All current EoL treatment scenarios are without Mn recovery
(Partially) existing or potential EoL treatment scenario with CRM recovery		Hydrometallurgy and pyrometallurgy (if lithium is recovered from slag)	Hydrometallurgy and pyrometallurgy	Theoretically possible, when undergoing hydrometallurgical process	Hydrometallurgy and pyrometallurgy	Al current collector foil separation during pre-treatment and subsequent remelting	Hydrometallurgy and pyrometallurgy	Theoretically possible, when undergoing hydrometallurgical process	Theoretically possible, when undergoing hydrometallurgical process
Nb.	Criteria (affecting recoverability)	How to evaluate the criteria?							
5.4	Recycling conflicts with hazardous substances	Is there a recycling conflict with hazardous substances? Are there hazardous substances in the respective application/waste flow? Will there be hazardous substances liberated during the recovery process? Can the hazardous substances be contained adequately?	# Decomposition of the binder polyvinylidene fluoride during thermal treatment--> Hydrogen fluoride (HF); Nickel oxide (carcinogenic) # Exothermic decomposition of conducting salt LiPF ₆ during thermal treatment --> LiF (Lithiumfluorid); PF5 (Phosphorpentafluorid) (Harnisch & Diekmann, 2014)	# Decomposition of the binder polyvinylidene fluoride during thermal treatment--> Hydrogen fluoride (HF); Nickel oxide (carcinogenic) # Exothermic decomposition of conducting salt LiPF ₆ during thermal treatment --> LiF (Lithiumfluorid); PF5 (Phosphorpentafluorid) (Harnisch & Diekmann, 2014)	# Decomposition of the binder polyvinylidene fluoride during thermal treatment--> Hydrogen fluoride (HF); Nickel oxide (carcinogenic) # Exothermic decomposition of conducting salt LiPF ₆ during thermal treatment --> LiF (Lithiumfluorid); PF5 (Phosphorpentafluorid) (Harnisch & Diekmann, 2014)	# Decomposition of the binder polyvinylidene fluoride during thermal treatment--> Hydrogen fluoride (HF); Nickel oxide (carcinogenic) # Exothermic decomposition of conducting salt LiPF ₆ during thermal treatment --> LiF (Lithiumfluorid); PF5 (Phosphorpentafluorid) (Harnisch & Diekmann, 2014)	# Decomposition of the binder polyvinylidene fluoride during thermal treatment--> Hydrogen fluoride (HF); Nickel oxide (carcinogenic) # Exothermic decomposition of conducting salt LiPF ₆ during thermal treatment --> LiF (Lithiumfluorid); PF5 (Phosphorpentafluorid) (Harnisch & Diekmann, 2014)	# Decomposition of the binder polyvinylidene fluoride during thermal treatment--> Hydrogen fluoride (HF); Nickel oxide (carcinogenic) # Exothermic decomposition of conducting salt LiPF ₆ during thermal treatment --> LiF (Lithiumfluorid); PF5 (Phosphorpentafluorid) (Harnisch & Diekmann, 2014)	# Decomposition of the binder polyvinylidene fluoride during thermal treatment--> Hydrogen fluoride (HF); Nickel oxide (carcinogenic) # Exothermic decomposition of conducting salt LiPF ₆ during thermal treatment --> LiF (Lithiumfluorid); PF5 (Phosphorpentafluorid) (Harnisch & Diekmann, 2014)
5.5	Environmental impacts	What are the environmental impacts of the 2CRM in comparison with the primary CRM? Is there any implemented/standardized calculation pathway for environmental impact assessment?	# Complex question and highly dependent on numerous factors, such as location of primary production, recycling technology, location of recycling facility, input feed, etc. # Secondary materials, via recycling, can help reduce primary supply requirements and alleviate the environmental burdens associated with the extraction and processing of materials from primary sources, where direct recycling offers the lowest impacts, followed by hydrometallurgical and pyrometallurgical. (Llamas-Orozco et al., 2023)	# Complex question and highly dependent on numerous factors, such as location of primary production, recycling technology, location of recycling facility, input feed, etc. # Secondary materials, via recycling, can help reduce primary supply requirements and alleviate the environmental burdens associated with the extraction and processing of materials from primary sources, where direct recycling offers the lowest impacts, followed by hydrometallurgical and pyrometallurgical. (Llamas-Orozco et al., 2023)	# Complex question and highly dependent on numerous factors, such as location of primary production, recycling technology, location of recycling facility, input feed, etc. # Secondary materials, via recycling, can help reduce primary supply requirements and alleviate the environmental burdens associated with the extraction and processing of materials from primary sources, where direct recycling offers the lowest impacts, followed by hydrometallurgical and pyrometallurgical. (Llamas-Orozco et al., 2023)	# Complex question and highly dependent on numerous factors, such as location of primary production, recycling technology, location of recycling facility, input feed, etc. # Secondary materials, via recycling, can help reduce primary supply requirements and alleviate the environmental burdens associated with the extraction and processing of materials from primary sources, where direct recycling offers the lowest impacts, followed by hydrometallurgical and pyrometallurgical. (Llamas-Orozco et al., 2023)	# Complex question and highly dependent on numerous factors, such as location of primary production, recycling technology, location of recycling facility, input feed, etc. # Secondary materials, via recycling, can help reduce primary supply requirements and alleviate the environmental burdens associated with the extraction and processing of materials from primary sources, where direct recycling offers the lowest impacts, followed by hydrometallurgical and pyrometallurgical. (Llamas-Orozco et al., 2023)	# Complex question and highly dependent on numerous factors, such as location of primary production, recycling technology, location of recycling facility, input feed, etc. # Secondary materials, via recycling, can help reduce primary supply requirements and alleviate the environmental burdens associated with the extraction and processing of materials from primary sources, where direct recycling offers the lowest impacts, followed by hydrometallurgical and pyrometallurgical. (Llamas-Orozco et al., 2023)	# Complex question and highly dependent on numerous factors, such as location of primary production, recycling technology, location of recycling facility, input feed, etc. # Secondary materials, via recycling, can help reduce primary supply requirements and alleviate the environmental burdens associated with the extraction and processing of materials from primary sources, where direct recycling offers the lowest impacts, followed by hydrometallurgical and pyrometallurgical. (Llamas-Orozco et al., 2023)
legal criteria									
6.1	Recovery targets	Are there material or element specific recovery targets?	# Battery Regulation: 50% by end 2027, 80% by end of 2031	# Battery Regulation: 90% by end 2027, 95% by end of 2031	No	# Battery Regulation: 90% by end 2027, 95% by end of 2031	No	# Battery Regulation: 90% by end 2027, 95% by end of 2031	No
6.2	Removal requirements	Are there any removal requirements related to the CRM containing application?	# Battery regulation: Requires portable batteries incorporated in appliances to be removable and replaceable by the end user by 2027 # Battery Regulation: Requires LMT batteries to be replaceable by an independent professional # EU Vehicle Directive: Requires vehicle design in a manner that enables battery removal and replacement by authorised treatment facilities or repair and maintenance operators	# Battery regulation: Requires portable batteries incorporated in appliances to be removable and replaceable by the end user by 2027 # Battery Regulation: Requires LMT batteries to be replaceable by an independent professional # EU Vehicle Directive: Requires vehicle design in a manner that enables battery removal and replacement by authorised treatment facilities or repair and maintenance operators	# Battery regulation: Requires portable batteries incorporated in appliances to be removable and replaceable by the end user by 2027 # Battery Regulation: Requires LMT batteries to be replaceable by an independent professional # EU Vehicle Directive: Requires vehicle design in a manner that enables battery removal and replacement by authorised treatment facilities or repair and maintenance operators	# Battery regulation: Requires portable batteries incorporated in appliances to be removable and replaceable by the end user by 2027 # Battery Regulation: Requires LMT batteries to be replaceable by an independent professional # EU Vehicle Directive: Requires vehicle design in a manner that enables battery removal and replacement by authorised treatment facilities or repair and maintenance operators	# Battery regulation: Requires portable batteries incorporated in appliances to be removable and replaceable by the end user by 2027 # Battery Regulation: Requires LMT batteries to be replaceable by an independent professional # EU Vehicle Directive: Requires vehicle design in a manner that enables battery removal and replacement by authorised treatment facilities or repair and maintenance operators	# Battery regulation: Requires portable batteries incorporated in appliances to be removable and replaceable by the end user by 2027 # Battery Regulation: Requires LMT batteries to be replaceable by an independent professional # EU Vehicle Directive: Requires vehicle design in a manner that enables battery removal and replacement by authorised treatment facilities or repair and maintenance operators	# Battery regulation: Requires portable batteries incorporated in appliances to be removable and replaceable by the end user by 2027 # Battery Regulation: Requires LMT batteries to be replaceable by an independent professional # EU Vehicle Directive: Requires vehicle design in a manner that enables battery removal and replacement by authorised treatment facilities or repair and maintenance operators
6.3	Legal incentives	Are there any legal incentives for the recovery of the CRM such as special facilities in application, permission or registration processes?	If considered as strategic project under the CRM Act, projects can benefit from streamlined and predictable permitting procedures and support in gaining access to finance. Furthermore, the requirement for recycled content in batteries in the Battery Regulation can act as incentive for recycling projects.	If considered as strategic project under the CRM Act, projects can benefit from streamlined and predictable permitting procedures and support in gaining access to finance. Furthermore, the requirement for recycled content in batteries in the Battery Regulation can act as incentive for recycling projects.	If considered as strategic project under the CRM Act, projects can benefit from streamlined and predictable permitting procedures and support in gaining access to finance.	If considered as strategic project under the CRM Act, projects can benefit from streamlined and predictable permitting procedures and support in gaining access to finance. Furthermore, the requirement for recycled content in batteries in the Battery Regulation can act as incentive for recycling projects.	No	No	If considered as strategic project under the CRM Act, projects can benefit from streamlined and predictable permitting procedures and support in gaining access to finance.
6.4	End-of-waste criteria	Are there established end-of-waste criteria for 2CRM?	No	No	No	No	Metal Scrap Regulation	Copper Scrap Regulation	No

target CRM	Li	Co	Graphite	Ni	Al	Cu	P	Mn
<i>application/waste flow</i>	<i>cathode active material (CAM) in Li rechargeable batteries</i>	<i>cathode active material (CAM) in Li rechargeable batteries</i>	<i>anode active material (AAM) in Li rechargeable batteries</i>	<i>cathode active material (CAM) in Li rechargeable batteries</i>	<i>cathode current collector (CCC), casing, and partly cathode active material (CAM) in Li rechargeable batteries</i>	<i>anode current collector (ACC) and cables in Li rechargeable batteries</i>	<i>cathode active material (CAM) in Li rechargeable batteries</i>	<i>cathode active material (CAM) in Li rechargeable batteries</i>
<i>EoL treatment scenario without CRM recovery</i>	<i>Pyrometallurgy: Recent pyrometallurgical processes, in which Li ends up in slag, do not recover Li from the slag Black mass export: A vast majority of batteries are mechanically pre-treated to obtain black mass, which is then exported (containing Li, Co, Mn, Ni, P, etc.).</i>	<i>Black mass export: A vast majority of batteries are mechanically pre-treated to obtain black mass, which is then exported (containing Li, Co, Mn, Ni, P, etc.).</i>	<i>All current EoL treatment scenarios are without graphite recovery</i>	<i>Black mass export: A vast majority of batteries are mechanically pre-treated to obtain black mass, which is then exported (containing Li, Co, Mn, Ni, P, etc.).</i>	<i>Pyrometallurgy: Recent pyrometallurgical processes, in which Al ends up in slag, do not recover Al from the slag. Al in cathode material not recovered at all.</i>	<i>unlikely scenario</i>	<i>All current EoL treatment scenarios are without P recovery</i>	<i>All current EoL treatment scenarios are without Mn recovery</i>
<i>(Partially) existing or potential EoL treatment scenario with CRM recovery</i>	<i>Hydrometallurgy and pyrometallurgy (if lithium is recovered from slag)</i>	<i>Hydrometallurgy and pyrometallurgy</i>	<i>Theoretically possible, when undergoing hydrometallurgical process</i>	<i>Hydrometallurgy and pyrometallurgy</i>	<i>Al current collector foil separation during pre-treatment and subsequent remelting</i>	<i>Hydrometallurgy and pyrometallurgy</i>	<i>Theoretically possible, when undergoing hydrometallurgical process</i>	<i>Theoretically possible, when undergoing hydrometallurgical process</i>
Nb.	Criteria (affecting recoverability)	How to evaluate the criteria?						

References mentioned in the table, for overarching references refer to the main report

(Romero Guillén et al., 2024)	Romero Guillén, D., Guimarães Sanches, J., Barbosa Botelho Junior, A., Gobo, L. A., Guimarães Bergerman, M., Romano Espinosa, D. C., & Tenório, J. A. S. (2024). Physical Process for Li-Ion Battery Recycling from Electric Vehicles. <i>Industrial and Engineering Chemistry Research</i> , 63(45), 19788–19803. https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.iecr.4c03271
Hanisch & Diekmann, 2014	Hanisch, C., & Diekmann, J. (2014). Recycling of Lithium-Ion Batteries (from Electric Vehicles). https://www.researchgate.net/publication/280644244
Llamas-Orozco et al., 2023	Llamas-Orozco, J. A., Meng, F., Walker, G. S., Abdul-Manan, A. F. N., MacLean, H. L., Posen, I. D., & McKechnie, J. (2023). Estimating the environmental impacts of global lithium-ion battery supply chain: A temporal, geographical, and technological perspective. <i>PNAS Nexus</i> , 2(11). https://doi.org/10.1093/pnasnexus/pgad361
Rinne et al., 2021	Rinne, M., Elomaa, H., Porvali, A., & Lundström, M. (2021). Simulation-based life cycle assessment for hydrometallurgical recycling of mixed LIB and NiMH waste. <i>Resources, Conservation and Recycling</i> , 170. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2021.105586
Wagner-Wenz et al., 2023	Wagner-Wenz, R., van Zuilichem, A. J., Göllner-Völker, L., Berberich, K., Weidenkaff, A., & Schebek, L. (2023). Recycling routes of lithium-ion batteries: A critical review of the development status, the process performance, and life-cycle environmental impacts. In <i>MRS Energy and Sustainability</i> (Vol. 10, Issue 1, pp. 1–34). Springer Nature. https://doi.org/10.1557/s43581-022-00053-9
Woeste et al., 2024	Woeste, R., Drude, E. S., Vrucak, D., Klöckner, K., Rombach, E., Letmathe, P., & Friedrich, B. (2024). A techno-economic assessment of two recycling processes for black mass from end-of-life lithium-ion batteries. <i>Applied Energy</i> , 361. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2024.122921
Battery Regulation (EU) 2023/1542	Regulation (EU) 2023/1542 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 July 2023 concerning batteries and waste batteries, amending Directive 2008/98/EC and Regulation (EU) 2019/1020 and repealing Directive 2006/66/EC
Copper Scrap Regulation (EU) No 715/2013	Commission Regulation (EU) No 715/2013 of 25 July 2013 establishing criteria determining when copper scrap ceases to be waste under Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council
CRM Act (EU) 2024/1252	Regulation (EU) 2024/1252 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 April 2024 establishing a framework for ensuring a secure and sustainable supply of critical raw materials and amending Regulations (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1724 and (EU) 2019/1020
Metal Scrap Regulation (EU) No 333/2011	Council Regulation (EU) No 333/2011 of 31 March 2011 establishing criteria determining when certain types of scrap metal cease to be waste under Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council

Abbreviations used

AAM	Anode Active Material
ACC	Anode Current Collector
AIB	Aluminium-ion battery
CAM	Cathode Active Material
CCC	Cathode Current Collector
CRM	Critical Raw Material
DPP	Digital Product Passport
EoL	End-of-life
EPR	Extended Producer Responsibility
EU	European Union
EV	Electric Vehicle
HPA	High Purity Alumina
LCA	Lithium-Cobalt-Aluminum
LFP	Lithium-Iron-Phosphate
LIB	Lithium-ion battery
LIBS	Laser-induced breakdown spectroscopy
LMFP	Lithium-Manganese-Iron-Phosphate
LMO	Lithium-Manganese-Oxide
LMT	Light Means of Transport
NMC	Nickel-Manganese-Cobalt
SIB	Sodium-ion battery
SLI	Starting, Lighting, and Ignition
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
XRF	X-ray fluorescence
XRT	X-ray transmission